

Modes of motion and impedance matching associated with energy transfer from outer hair cells

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Abstract. Outer hair cells (OHCs) are much softer than the basilar membrane (BM). The effectiveness of OHCs as an amplifier is limited by this mismatch if they are elements of a system, which undergoes a single mode of motion. This limitation is particularly acute in the high frequency region near the base of the cochlea. Recent experiments, particularly with OCT method, revealed that the motion in the cochlea is complex. This leads to a question, "Can multiple modes of motion facilitate energy transfer from OHCs?" As a proof of concept, simple coupled oscillators are examined here.

INTRODUCTION

A focus on theoretical cochlear mechanics has been the question of how to incorporate outer hair cells (OHCs) into the rest of the cochlea [1]. A good number of early models assume that OHCs apply force directly on the basilar membrane (BM) [2, 3]. Such macroscopic models do not consider the microscopic structure of the organ of Corti, which includes OHCs and cannot incorporate detailed properties of OHCs. Micromechanics, which incorporates detailed structural factors, opens up a number of basic issues regarding OHCs, such as how fast OHCs can respond and the effectiveness of power transmission. The issue of the effectiveness of power transmission from OHCs to the vibration of the inner ear stems from a disparity in stiffness: OHCs are much softer than the BM, which is important for frequency tuning. The present report examines this issue based on coupled oscillator models, which are the simplest examples of a system with multiple modes of motion.

THE THEORY

Consider a system of two coupled harmonic oscillators, heavy and light. The heavy oscillator (HO) consists of the BM, the major inertial mass, and the major viscous drag. The light oscillator (LO) has less inertial mass and weaker elastic element and incorporates an OHC. These two oscillators would be coupled with a viscoelastic element. However, let us assume that it is either viscous or elastic for simplicity. Assume also that the behavior of OHCs is described by a recently developed biophysical model [4].

Force generated by OHC

Consider an OHC is associated with an oscillator, which has mass m , drag coefficient η , and elastic element with stiffness k_e . The equation of motion can be expressed as

$$\left(m \frac{d^2}{dt^2} + \eta \frac{d}{dt} + k_e + k_o \right) X = F_{\text{OHC}} + F, \quad (1)$$

where X is the position of the mass, F external driving force. The OHC has the intrinsic stiffness k_o and exerts force F_{OHC} elicited by the bending of its hair bundle.

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FIGURE 1. Two rendering, exact (left) and approximate (right), of the single oscillator equation. The oscillator consists of mass m , an external elastic element with stiffness k_e , and a damper with drag coefficient η and an outer hair cell (OHC) with material stiffness k_o . This system is driven by a sinusoidal waveform (wavy blue arrow). Left: the exact connectivity, from which the equation is derived. The external elastic element and the OHC share the same force and displacement while the speed of the mass is null. Right: Such a condition is approximately satisfied by the connectivity on the left only if the condition $k_e \lesssim k_o$ is satisfied.

Let driving force F have a sinusoidal waveform with angular frequency ω . Then the position X must have also a sinusoidal component x .

$$F = F_0 + f \exp[i\omega t], \quad (2a)$$

$$X = X_0 + x \exp[i\omega t]. \quad (2b)$$

The equation of motion can be expressed as

$$\left(-\bar{\omega}^2 + i\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}\eta + 1 + \gamma B\right)x = i\frac{\gamma A}{\bar{\omega}}\hat{r} + f/(k_e + k_o), \quad (3)$$

where frequencies with overlines, such as $\bar{\omega}$ etc, are frequencies normalized by the resonance frequency ω_r . $\bar{\omega}\eta$ is normalized viscoelastic frequency, and \hat{r} is the amplitude of the relative hair bundle resistance. Active force F_{OHC} produced by the OHC gives rise to terms that contain parameters A and B [4, 5]. Parameter A is inversely related to the resonance frequency whereas B is independent of it. The quantity γ , which takes unity as the maximum value, is the operating point variable for OHC electromotility. The first term on the right-hand-side works similar to negative drag with inverse frequency dependence, owing its dependence on the receptor potential.

Single oscillator (SO) model

This case assumes that both OHC and BM are elements of a single oscillator (SO) together with a damper. Since the hair bundle is stimulated by the displacement of the oscillator, we have $\hat{r} = gx$. That leads to the equation of motion

$$\left(-\bar{\omega}^2 + i\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}\eta + 1 + \gamma B\right)x = i\frac{\gamma Ag}{\bar{\omega}}x + f/(k_e + k_o). \quad (4)$$

Power gain $G(\omega)$ is calculated as the ratio of power output to power input. Power output can be defined as viscous loss $\eta|dX/dt|^2$ because the other component is recovered during a cycle. Power input can be expressed $\text{Re}[F \cdot dX/dt]$.

Coupled oscillators

The heavy oscillator (HO) includes a stiff elastic element and has viscous damping. The displacement of this oscillator is represented by Y . The light oscillator (LO) includes a soft elastic element and an OHC. The displacement of this oscillator is represented by X .

$$\left(m\frac{d^2}{dt^2} + k + k_o\right)X = F_{\text{OHC}} + \left(k_c + \eta_c\frac{d}{dt}\right)(Y - X) \quad (5a)$$

$$\left(M\frac{d^2}{dt^2} + \eta\frac{d}{dt} + K\right)Y = \left(k_c + \eta_c\frac{d}{dt}\right)(X - Y) + F(t). \quad (5b)$$

Now, assume force F is periodic, as expressed by Eq. 2a. Then as in the case of SO, OHC force F_{OHC} consists of two components. One is additional stiffness term for LO, where the OHC is located. This term is proportional to B .

FIGURE 2. Coupled oscillators. Two possible connectivities are shown. The simpler connectivity on the right is likely more physiologically relevant. The outer hair cell (OHC) is driven by the movement of either by HO (left) or LO (right) as shown by dashed red arrows. OHC is an element in LO and the stiff basilar membrane is an element of HO. HO is driven by a sinusoidal waveform with angular frequency ω (wavy blue arrow). The two oscillators are coupled either by an elastic element with stiffness k_c or a dashpot with viscous coefficient η_c .

parameter	function	parameter	function
$\bar{\omega} = \omega/\omega_r$	normalized frequency	$0 < \gamma < 1$	operating point variable
A	amplifying parameter	$\hat{r} \ll 1$	change in HB resistance
B	shifting parameter	r_L	elastic load ratio
m, M	inertial mass	k, K	stiffness
$\omega_r = \sqrt{K/M}$	resonance freq.	$\omega_L^2 = k/m$	LO resonance freq.
k_c	coupling stiffness	η	drag coefficient
$s = K/k$	stiffness ratio	η_c	coupling drag
$\omega_\eta = K/\eta$	roll off frequency	$\bar{\omega}_\eta = \omega_\eta/\omega_r$	normalized roll-off

TABLE I. Variables and parameters

The other component is proportional to $A\hat{r}$, which applies active force to LO. In the LO-driven case, $\hat{r} = gx$ and in the HO-driven case $\hat{r} = gy$, assuming they share the same coefficient g .

For LO-driven oscillators, the equations of motion turn into

$$[-(\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_1)^2 + i(s\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_c - \gamma Ag/\bar{\omega}) + 1 + cs + \gamma B]x - (is\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_c - cs)y = 0, \quad (6a)$$

$$-(i\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_c + c)x + [-\bar{\omega}^2 + i(\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_\eta + \bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_c) + 1 + c]y = f_B, \quad (6b)$$

where the frequency with overline is normalized by the resonance frequency $\omega_r = \sqrt{K/M}$. Other parameters include $s = k/K$, $c = k_c/K$, $\omega_c = K/\eta_c$, and $f_B = f/K$. The special case of $c = 0$ corresponds to viscosity coupling and $1/\bar{\omega}_c = 0$ to elasticity coupling.

For HO-driven oscillators, the equations of motion turns into

$$[-(\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_1)^2 + 1 + cs + is\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_c + \gamma B]x - [i(\gamma Ag/\bar{\omega} + s\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_c) + cs]y = 0, \quad (7a)$$

$$-(i\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_c + c)x + [-\bar{\omega}^2 + i(\bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_\eta + \bar{\omega}/\bar{\omega}_c) + 1 + c]y = f_B. \quad (7b)$$

Similar to Eq. 6, the special case of $c = 0$ corresponds to viscosity coupling and $1/\bar{\omega}_c = 0$ to elasticity coupling.

For these coupled oscillators, power gain $G(\omega)$ is obtained from y , the amplitude of HO because HO is directly involved in both input and output.

NUMERICAL EXAMINATION

For this study, the 20 kHz location ($\omega_r/2\pi = 2 \times 10^4$) of the guinea pig cochlea is chosen because the values of cellular and structural parameters are available [4, 5]. These values for load-free condition are

$$Ag_{20} = 1.36 \quad B_{20} = 2.13 \quad \omega_\eta/\omega_r = 0.1. \quad (8)$$

An elastic load on the OHC attenuates these parameters. If we let r_L be the ratio of the external elastic load to the stiffness of the OHC, we have

$$Ag = Ag_{20} \cdot \frac{1}{1 + r_L}, \quad B = B_{20} \frac{r_L}{1 + r_L}. \quad (9)$$

Notice that the factor A is significantly attenuated as load increases, whereas the factor B is much less affected.

FIGURE 3. Amplitude of SO plotted against frequency normalized to resonance frequency ω_r . The value of γ , the operating point variable increases from 0.1 (left) to 0.8 (right) with increment of 0.1. Unit of amplitude is $f/(k_e + k_o)$. See Eq. 4. The value of parameter A is approximately twice as large for 10 kHz than for 20 kHz because of the 2-fold difference in the resonance frequency. The values of parameter B are similar for both cases.

FIGURE 4. Single mode oscillator (SO) at 20 kHz. Peak amplitude (A), peak frequency (B), peak phase with respect to force input (C), and the ratio of power output to power input (D) plotted against γ , the operating point variable. The unit of the amplitude is the ratio to the input f/K .

Single Oscillator (SO) model

With parameter values for 10 kHz, the amplitude increase with an increase in the operating point γ of the OHC (Fig. 3A). However, with the parameter values for 20 kHz, that is not the case (Figs. 3B, 4A). That is consistent with a previous report, which reports that 10 kHz is the limiting frequency with the single mode oscillator [4]. The peak frequency shifts higher as γ increases (Fig. 4B). The phase of the peak is $-\pi/2$ consistent with resonance condition (Fig. 4C). Power gain does not increase significantly from unity at $\gamma = 0$.

Coupled oscillators

LO-driven oscillators can show significant gains in amplitude from SO for both oscillators if they are elasticity-coupled (Fig. 5A in left panel). The amplitude gain of LO is slightly larger than that of HO in both cases. The peak amplitude is in general an increasing function of γ , the operating point variable. However, it can peak before γ reaches unity. Viscosity coupled oscillators do achieve some gains but it is not as effective as elasticity coupled ones (Fig. 5 A in right panel). In both cases both oscillator share the peak frequencies (Fig. 5B). The peak phase of LO is ahead of HO with elastic coupling. That indicates that LO amplifies HO. The small difference is the result of strong coupling. With viscous coupling, the phase of HO and that of LO are rather similar because force applied from LO to HO advanced from the phase of LO by $\pi/2$. The power gain goes down as γ , the operating point variable, approaches null in both cases. While the elasticity coupled oscillator tends to unity as γ approaches null, the viscosity coupled oscillator tends to a value below unity because a part of input power is lost from the coupling element.

HO-driven oscillators show a good gain in amplitude with elastic coupling (Fig. 6A). Again the amplitude LO is higher than that of HO. The amplitude of HO can be larger than that of LO, unlike LO-driven oscillators. The peak frequency shifts upward as γ increases (Fig. 6B). However with viscous coupling the shift is much less (right panel). LO is ahead of HO with elastic coupling and the relationship is the opposite with viscous coupling (Fig. 6B).

FIGURE 5. LO-driven oscillators, elasticity coupled (left) and viscosity coupled (right). A: The gain of the amplitude of HO (blue) and LO (red) over SO, plotted against γ , the operating point variable. B: Peak frequency similar to elasticity. C: Peak phase with respect to input waveform. D: The ratio of power output to power input. coupled oscillators. Parameter values are $k_c/K = 0.5$, $\omega_1 = 0.25$ for elasticity coupled oscillators (left) and $\eta_c/\eta = 0.6$, $\omega_1 = 0.31$ for viscosity coupled oscillators (right).

FIGURE 6. HO-driven oscillators, elasticity coupled (left) and viscosity coupled (right). A: The gain of the amplitude of HO (blue) and LO (red) over SO, plotted against γ , the operating point variable. B: Peak frequency similar to elasticity. C: Peak phase with respect to input waveform. D: The ratio of power output to power input. coupled oscillators. Parameter values are $k_c/K = 0.25$, $\omega_1 = 0.3$ for elasticity coupled oscillators (left) and $\eta_c/\eta = 0.2$, $\omega_1 = 0.34$ for viscosity coupled oscillators (right).

DISCUSSION

The present numerical examination performed corresponds to the condition of the 20 kHz region in the cochlea of guinea pigs. Even though a system of coupled oscillators can in all four cases improve power output of OHCs, Elasticity couples oscillators are much more effective than viscosity couples ones. In contrast to about 60-fold power gain that is achieved by elasticity coupled oscillators, the gain obtained by viscosity coupled oscillators is only about two fold.

In all four cases, the amplitudes of the two oscillators are similar, peaking at almost identical frequencies. In addition, phase differences are relatively small. These features, which are the result of strong coupling, are reminiscent of a simple macroscopic model, which ignores both the low-pass characteristics of OHCs and the stiffness mismatch between OHCs and the BM.

A basic assumption of the models examined here is that the main viscous drag is associated with HO. If the main

drag is associated with LO, then LO has no influence on the movement of HO. An issue is the origin of the viscous drag. HO-driven coupled oscillators are compatible with the assumption that the main drag originates from shear motion in the subtectorial space because it assumes that the subtectorial shear stimulates the hair bundles of OHCs. LO-driven oscillators, however, need an assumption that the movement of LO does not incur the main drag. That requires an assumption that the water that is displaced by the movement of OHCs can be accommodated locally by a local displacement of the tectorial membrane. The anisotropy and heterogeneity of the tectorial membrane could allow such displacements.

Some of the cases can be superposed, while retaining the effectiveness. In particular, LO-driven oscillators with elastic coupling appears compatible with HO-driven oscillators with elastic coupling because their phase relationships are similar.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study analyzes the simplest cases of a system with multiple modes of motion. the result could be generalized as follows:

- Multiple modes of motion can overcome the limitation imposed by impedance mismatch of the single oscillator mode, extending the frequency limit of OHCs as the cochlear amplifier.
- The behavior of these coupled oscillators can be highly sensitive to values of some of the parameters.
- Small differences in the phase relationship are indicative of the nature of the amplifying mechanism.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Lisa Olson: "Is HO the basilar membrane (BM) and what is LO?"

The approach taken by this paper, is in my opinion, opposite of most theories in cochlea mechanics. Instead of a precisely defined structural model, it starts from a minimalist model that HO is associated with the BM and LO is associated with OHCs to seek configurations and conditions, or models, for effective functioning of OHCs. I hope such an approach is complementary to more authentic approaches of cochlear mechanics.

One of the findings is that strong elastic coupling between HO and LO is advantageous for the performance. This could be interpreted that Deiters' cells together with Deiters' cup performs better as an elastic element. Alternatively, it could be the phalangeal process that provide the elastic element.

[Renata Sisto] "In eq (5b) left hand side you should substitute X with Y." "In the coupled oscillators model, you insert an elastic coupling that is also an internal force between the LO and the HO. The F_{OHC} acts instead only on the LO, being activated by the hair bundle radial motion. As the OHC body is something connecting the BM to the RL, what is the reason for not introducing the force exerted by the OHC as an internal one? In analogy with the elastic

coupling proportional to the oscillators relative displacement ($X - Y$)? Is there any strong evidence for making this choice?"

The idea that "to connect the OHC with the BM directly" results in the model that these two elements form the same oscillator. That is exactly the Single mode oscillator, the performance of which is limited by impedance mismatch between the two elements.

For this reason, the link between the two is treated as the coupling of the two oscillators. Gain optimization leads to strong coupling of the two oscillators and the phase difference is rather small as the result. However, this small phase difference of the two oscillators is essential for the amplifying role of the OHC.

[Wen Cai] "If I understand correctly, the introduced coupled element (k_c, η_c) simulates the function of Deiters' cells. In this case, the results indicate that it is better for the Deiters' cells to function like a spring."

Yes, the best gain is obtained if Deiters' cell behave like a spring. However, that applies to high frequency locations. At low frequencies the difference in gain between those cases become smaller and the gain alone may not be the decisive factor.

"Why and how does the OHC force relate to the HO (BM) displacement y ? My understanding is that the OHC force is related to its length change, which is a function of x , not y ."

The dependence of OHC output on y comes from $\hat{r} = gy$ with HO stimulation.

[Jont Allen] "Is the instability that you mentioned related to Hopf bifurcation?"

That is an interesting idea, but no, the equations used here are linear ones for small displacements because they are derived under the condition that a system is not too far from its equilibrium.

The instability that I mentioned is that a small difference in some of the parameters in the organ of Corti results in sharp peaking of output plotted against the operating point parameter. It may not be related to the uneven gain along the lateral axis, which is one of the mechanisms for otoacoustic emission. Nonetheless, it is a curious observation, which may not be ignored.

[Alessandro Altoè] "Why viscous loss is used to calculate power gain?"

In a local model in steady state, input power must be used up as viscous loss because elastic components is recovered after a cycle. Input power has two sources. The sum of the explicit mechanical input (the product of the force and the velocity of HO) and implicit OHC input, which increases the amplitude of HO, must be equal to viscous loss by HO. Indeed, in the absence of OHC output, the explicit mechanical input is equal to the viscous loss, i.e. no power gain. Thus, power gain can be obtained by the ratio of viscous loss to the explicit mechanical power input.